

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF UNIVERSITIES AS THE FOUNDATION FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article discusses issues related to the development of innovation capacity, improvement of the education quality and competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions. The essence of the innovative strategy of higher educational institutions that should be built taking into account modern requirements of the market and to outstrip the demand for research and educational activities is revealed.

Key words: innovation, innovation management in education, competitiveness, innovation education, economics.

Introduction.

The modern socio-economic development of Uzbekistan requires higher educational institutions to significantly improve their creative potential and increase the competitiveness of their graduates. The solution of this problem involves the formation of an innovative educational environment in the modern system of higher education. A set of measures that ensure the formation of such an environment can become a solution to many problems related to the improvement of the educational process and become one of the main sources of economic development of the country. The reform of higher education in order to increase the intellectual potential of the country dictates the need to switch to an innovative path of development. Further development of higher education requires the introduction of new forms and methods of teaching focused on the quality of the educational and practical component of the curricula, making adjustments to the existing system of higher

education. Management of innovative development of higher educational institutions is based on scientific and methodological provisions that require serious consideration and adjustment taking into account modern conditions. Modern domestic researchers have different views on the solution of this problem. Nevertheless, they all agree that in order to increase the competitiveness of higher educational institutions themselves in the conditions of the modern market of educational services, it is necessary to develop methods for managing the innovative development of educational activities of the university. These methods should be based on the integration of training with scientific research, with production activities, and also contribute to increasing entrepreneurial activity through the formation of innovative thinking among graduates. In the current economic situation, more and more specialists engaged in the innovative sector of the economy say that the basis of effective innovative development is not economic mechanisms and levers, but first of all people with the necessary knowledge and engaged in the implementation of the national innovation system. Thus, the task of improving the education system arises, and the problem of personnel training becomes particularly relevant: innovative managers, innovative projects in education, the creation of strong and stable links between research centers and educational organizations, as well as prospective employers. In addition, higher education institutions, operating in an increasingly competitive environment, primarily related to demographic changes, are forced to revise existing methods of training bachelors and masters. The management system of universities should also be adjusted to meet modern market requirements. The market, as you know, dictates its requirements based on the existing or emerging demand from consumers. The possibility of using an innovative system of higher education that is ahead of the development in order to improve

quality will significantly change the role of higher education in the development of innovative activities. This system will help in solving many socio-economic problems by creating an effective mechanism for using scientific and technical potential. Higher education institutions have a crucial role to play in the implementation of a knowledge-based economic growth strategy and in the formation of a democratic and socially interconnected society. Higher education contributes to the improvement of the institutional regime through the training of competent and responsible specialists who are required for the skillful management of macroeconomics and the public sector. When developing new innovative educational programs based on a competence-based approach, new training courses, modules and innovative methods will be required, which make it possible to develop new programs of academic disciplines and introduce new innovative techniques into existing courses based on a combination of theoretical knowledge with practical work skills. All this will require the creation of a system of innovative methods for the development of educational programs in the field of information technology, economics and management, in which new innovative technologies are used. The development and use of new educational programs involves the creation and introduction into the educational process of educational and methodological complexes of disciplines, programs of production and training practices in all implemented areas and specialties, taking into account the rapidly changing market requirements and socio-economic conditions. This will allow us to build the educational process on the basis of the author's methodological developments, taking into account all the conditions for the functioning of future graduates. The development of new innovative educational programs will require the creation and introduction into the educational process of educational and methodological

complexes (UMK), programs of industrial practices in disciplines and specialties, developed taking into account modern, rapidly changing socio-economic conditions. This event provides for the systematization of educational and methodological documents and allows you to build the educational process on a solid methodological basis and systematically implement its practical implementation. The work on the creation of the UMK should be considered as a fundamental stage aimed at further improving the quality of training of specialists with higher education. Higher educational institutions that fully possess the entire set and functionality of innovative technologies that can solve several fundamental problems can and should become the basic intellectual structure that contributes to solving the tasks set. In particular, they should become: - the basis for the creation and deployment of a national innovation system; - a tool to increase the economy's receptivity to innovation and create a public need for the use of high-class and world-class specialists in Uzbekistan; - a base for training specialists for the public administration system, for scientific support of state decisions; - a factor that increases the role of the education system in the development and implementation of industrial, scientific and innovation policy; - a flexible link between the largest domestic and transnational corporations, the educational and scientific community of Uzbekistan; - the main link in the training of the national scientific and technical, intellectual elite with a deep innovative culture; - an element capable of perceiving and creatively developing the domestic and foreign experience of organizing higher education at a new level;

- a means to increase the manageability and activity of the entire higher education system in scientific, innovative, methodological terms; - a tool that can give a new impetus to the traditional areas of education reform. The main task of higher educational institutions should be the development and testing of scientific

and methodological, organizational, economic and legal principles and fundamental provisions in achieving the goals listed above, in the general context of the reforms carried out in modern Uzbekistan. In other words, in the modern socio-economic conditions of an innovative economy based on knowledge and a sharp increase in the pace of scientific and technological progress, the main innovation strategy of a modern university should be: conducting scientific research, training highly qualified specialists using high-tech innovative technologies of education and materialization (commercialization) of the results of research work. The transition of higher educational institutions to an innovative path of development is a fundamental factor of successful activity in modern conditions. The concentration of attention only on the rational use of one's internal potential goes into the background in the management system of a higher educational institution, the transition to development consistent with the requirements of the labor market becomes paramount. The innovative strategy of higher educational institutions should outstrip the demand for scientific and educational activities and its essence should consist of consistent development of solutions that contribute to sustainable development. The lack of understanding of the need to develop an innovative strategy of activity becomes the reason for the insolvency of many universities. However, the mere understanding of the need will not be able to lead a higher educational institution to an innovative path of development. The management is required to clearly define the strategy and tactics, as well as to develop mutually dependent actions aimed at achieving the goals of innovative development. Continuous improvement of the quality of practical training of students in higher educational institutions by creating a clear university management system based on innovative development will contribute to solving social, economic, complex

engineering problems facing modern society. Modernization of higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan should ensure the successful integration of domestic universities into the global and pan-European educational space. Thus, the sustainable development of the entire higher education system should be considered as a branch of the national economy characterized by a formed economic and legal space.

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